

Brucella boot sock sampling

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Sock sampling protocol

1. The socks are packed in pairs (example: Agritamp Plus 02) one sock per boot of the person doing the sampling. The gaze-socks are water repelling, so a pair of boot socks is moistened with an appropriate volume of sterile PBS or water each to make them more absorbent.
2. In general, an area 15x100/20x100 meters is sampled with a pair of socks; so is recommended walking around following the pattern indicated in Figure 1. **It is important to cover as much a large area as possible.** It is important to walk through a large representative area. Walk through the field for the established entire perimeter and in the central part diagonally in order to travel a distance representative of the entire area involved in the sampling.
3. Put the boot sock underneath the shoes plastic covering on a plastic sock.
4. Wear the boot sock properly as shown in Figure 2
5. After sampling, the socks are removed from the boots and put back in the plastic bag, which is sealed and tagged (as shown in Figure 3)
6. The socks are stored 4 - 7°C until further processing

Figure 1 – es:The walking pattern for collecting sock samples in a broiler house.

Figure 2 – The socks are packed in pairs in clean plastic bags. Each sock is taken from the back and put over one shoe as shown is pictures

Figure 3 – To remove the sock after sampling, simply put on a plastic glove and pull it off. The socks are put back in the plastic bag, remember to seal and tag it, and store at 4 - 7°C.

Cultural method for boot socks:

1. The pair, left and right boot socks, are pooled and analysed together as one sample.
2. Put the boot sock pair in a suitable container. Add Selective Brucella broth (1:10 ratio, equivalent to 1+9 volume).
3. After 5 days of incubation: Plate out a loopful (10 μ l) of the initial suspension onto at least 3 agar plates (Farrel) and repeat on a second agar of choice. Incubate the plates at 37°C with 5% of CO₂.
4. Confirmation of colonies: Pick up a total of three colonies confirm with your the routine testing (PCR, MALDI, or biochemical identification).

Incubate for 5 days

PCR method for boot socks:

The boot socks, the pair (left and right shoes) of boot socks are pooled and analysed together as one sample.

Low contaminated soil samples

- Dilute each boot (L and R) 1:10 with nuclease free water in Stomacher Bags with filter.
- Process in Stomacher® instrument for 60 seconds.
- Take 2 ml from the stomacher bag,
- Centrifuge at 13.000 rpm (15.870 rcf) for 5/7 min.
- Remove the supernatant and resuspend the pellet in 200 µl nuclease free water

High contaminated soil samples

- Dilute each boot (L and R) 1:10 with nuclease free water sterile Stomacher Bags with filter
- Process in Stomacher® instrument for 60 seconds.
- Take 300 µl from the stomacher bag,
- Centrifuge at 13.000 rpm (15.870 rcf) for 5/7 min.
- Remove the supernatant and resuspend the pellet in 200 µl nuclease free water

